

Research Paper: Effects of Physical Activity Participation on Fine and Gross Motor Skills in Pre-School Children with ADHD

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the association between physical activity with fine and gross motor skills in pre-school children with ADHD. The present study is a descriptive-correlational study. The participants were 58 children (20 girls) aged 4 to 6 years who were selected using a convenience sampling method. We utilized Physical Activity Questionnaire for Children (PAQ-C) to measure physical activity. The short form of the Bruininks-Oseretsky Test of Motor Proficiency Ed. 2 (BOT-2) was used to measure the fine and gross motor. Independent *t* test and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. Children in this study had low levels of physical activity and motor proficiency. Boys had significantly higher physical activity and motor proficiency than girls ($P < 0.001$). In addition, physical activity was directly and significantly associated with fine and gross motor skills (both $P < 0.001$). These findings indicate that there is a need to increase the level of physical activity in pre-school children with ADHD, especially girls. Moreover, it is recommended that physical education teachers and sports coaches use programs in physical education lessons to facilitate motor skills in children.

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1. Introduction

In the first five years of their life, children develop in four main areas: motor (physical), communication and language, cognitive, and social-emotional (Brian et al. 2020; Seyedi Asl et al., 2016; Saeedpour-Parizi et al., 2020, 2021; Mohammadi et al., 2022; Hazrati et al., 2022; Hashemi Motlagh et al., 2022s). Motor development means physical growth and strengthening of bones, muscles and the child's ability to move and touch the surrounding environment (De Meester et al., 2018; Taghva et al., 2016). Motor skills are skills that enable movements and tasks that every human being performs from birth to old age. These skills are the movements that enable us to perform daily tasks, from the ability to eat to moving from one place to another (Gallotta et al., 2018). Normally, children learn certain motor skills at certain ages, however some children may be slow in acquiring motor skills due to various reasons including developmental delay (Baniyadi et al., 2022c; Chaharbaghi et al., 2022; Hernandez & Caçola, 2015; Khosravi et al., 2023). In general, motor skills are divided into two categories: fine motor skills and gross motor skills. Fine motor skills are skills that require high control and precision in the small muscles of the hand (such as using a fork). In gross motor skills, children use the large muscles of the body to build balance, coordination, reaction time, and body strength to perform larger movements such as walking and jumping (Baniyadi et al., 2022b; Chaharbaghi et al., 2022; Logan et al., 2011; Morley et al., 2015). The development of gross motor skills can be important for improving self-esteem and fine motor skills

for many daily tasks such as dressing, combing and writing (Mukherjee et al., 2017). During childhood, these skills provide a good opportunity to communicate with others and cooperate with them, and it has been proven that there is a direct relationship between positive social acceptability and movement capabilities, especially in boys (Baniyadi et al., 2022a; Guadagnoli et al., 2002; Seyedi Asl et al., 2021; Slotte et al., 2015). Children and adolescents with mobility problems face problems in performing gross motor skills, which results in their non-participation in sports, loss of physical fitness, withdrawal from society, and reduced self-esteem (Khosravi et al., 2023; Seyedi Asl et al., 2021; Venetsanou & Kambas, 2016, 2017; Wrotniak et al., 2016).

Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a group of biological-neurological disorders that disrupt the regulation of the level of activity, inhibition of behavior (impulsivity) and the range of a person's attention (Birchwood & Daley, 2012). This disorder is one of the first or second most common disorders of childhood and adolescence, with different variations and a prevalence of 3 to 10 percent in school-age children, and the severity of the disorder decreases in the ages above 10 years (Farhangnia et al., 2020). This disorder is three to nine times more common in boys than girls. One of the areas of attention in ADHD children is the physical and movement aspects that are studied by physical education specialists, doctors and rehabilitation centers (Goulardins et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021). Daily activities require sustained attention and impulse inhibition, so

children with ADHD may have difficulty in these actions. Several studies that have investigated the movement performance and movement processes of ADHD children have pointed out the weakness of balance and coordination, weakness of gross motor skills, weakness of fine motor skills and weakness of physical fitness indicators among these children (Mastoras et al., 2018; Sabzi et al., 2021).

One of the possible factors that can affect the development of children's motor skills is participation in physical activity. Basically, physical activity refers to any movement of the body that is caused by the contraction and expansion of the skeletal muscles and requires energy (Abdi et al., 2020; Basterfield et al., 2021; Gritten Campos et al., 2019). It has been extensively shown that physical activity is a key to reducing the risk of serious diseases, such as heart disease, stroke, diabetes and cancer in children (Dishman et al., 2009; Gallego-Méndez et al., 2020; Ghorbani et al., 2020; Haidar et al., 2019). Research shows that regular physical activity can increase a child's self-esteem, mood and sleep quality and make him less prone to stress, depression and dementia (Lahart et al., 2019; Schwartz et al., 2019; Sheikh et al., 2021, 2022; Wafa et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2021). However, the impact of physical activity on fine and gross skills in preschool children with ADHD has received less attention. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the effects of physical activity on fine and gross skills in preschool children with ADHD.

2. Methods

The method of current study was descriptive-correlation, which investigated the relationships between physical activity with fine and gross skills in preschool children with ADHD. The parents of children gave written consents for the participation of their children in this study. The protocol of this study was in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.1. Participants

The statistical population of the study consisted of all preschool children with ADHD who attended in a special preschool for exceptional children with behavioral disorders in Tehran. Of them, 58 children with ADHD (20 girls) aged 4-6 years old were selected using a convenience sampling method as the statistical population of this study.

2.2. Measures

Physical activity was measured using Physical Activity Questionnaire for Children (PAQ-C). This questionnaire was designed by Kowalski et al. (1997). This questionnaire contains 8 questions that the participants answered on a 5-point Likert scale. The validity of the questionnaire structure was confirmed through the confirmatory factor analysis and the high loading rate was over 0.4. Also, the reliability of the questionnaire was obtained through the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.86 (Kowalski et al., 1997).

The short form of the Bruininks-Oseretsky Test of Motor Proficiency Ed. 2 (BOT-2) was used to measure the motor proficiency of children. BOT-2 is a set of standard-reference tests that is used to measure the motor performance of children aged 4.5 to 14.5 years old. Bruininks (2005) designed this test

by modifying Oseretsky's motor proficiency test. It takes 15-20 minutes to complete the short form. The short form of this test has eight subtests and 14 items, which are part of the 46 items, which include abilities such as 1) running speed and agility (one item), 2) static and dynamic balance (two items), 3) coordination bilateral (two items), 4) leg muscle strength (one item), 5) upper limb coordination (two items), 6) reaction speed (one item), 7) visual-motor control (three items), and 8) upper limb agility and speed (measures two substances). Items 1 to 4 of the test are indicators of gross motor skills, items 6 to 8 are indicators of fine motor skills, and item 5 is a combination of both motor skills. The retest reliability coefficient of this test is 0.86 in the short form. This test has been standardized in Iran as well (Mohammadi Orangi et al. 2018). Each child receives a raw score, which is converted into points according to the guide table. The range of gross and fine motor skill scores is 0-53 and 0-51. A higher score means a better motor skill

2.3. Data analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 26. Mean and standard deviation were used for descriptive statistics. Independent t test was used for considering gender differences. Regression analysis was used to obtain the effect of the physical activity on fine and gross motor skills. P-value was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive data and gender differences

In Table 1, the descriptive characteristics of the participants, physical activity, fine motor skill, and gross motor skill of the boys and girls are shown. As appeared, boys and girls have almost identical age, height, and weight (all $P > 0.05$). However, boys had significantly higher levels of physical activity ($P < 0.001$), fine motor skill ($P < 0.001$), and gross motor skill ($P < 0.001$) than girls. Means of physical activity, fine motor skill ($P < 0.001$), and gross motor skill across genders are shown in Figure 1, 2, and 3.

Table 1
Descriptive data of the study

	Boys	Girls	Gender differences
Age (years)	5.25 ± 0.70	5.16 ± 0.81	t=0.269 P>0.05
Height (m)	1.09 ± 0.15	1.04 ± 0.10	t=0.193 P>0.05
Weight (kg)	20.33 ± 7.28	19.70 ± 6.38	t=0.634 P>0.05
Physical activity	2.25 ± 0.70	1.16 ± 0.81	t=-7.161* P<0.001
Fine motor skill	24.54 ± 4.28	20.16 ± 3.62	t=6.337* P<0.001
Gross motor skills	28.39 ± 5.28	24.16 ± 4.10	t=-5.727* P<0.001

Figure 1. Mean of physical activity across genders

Figure 2. Mean of fine motor skill across genders

Figure 3. Mean of gross motor skill across genders

3.2. Regression analysis

Regarding the regression analysis with forward selection, the results (Table 2) showed that physical activity has a direct and

significantly link with fine motor skill ($P < 0.001$). In addition, physical activity has a direct and significantly link with gross motor skill ($P < 0.001$).

Table 2

Results of regression analysis to discover the link between physical activity with fine and gross motor skills

		Coefficient	SE	Standardized Coefficient	P-values
Physical activity	Fine motor skill	-0.640	8.16	-0.621	<0.001
	Gross motor skill	0.552	6.02	0.522	<0.001

4. Discussion

The purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between physical activity and fine and gross motor skills in preschool children with ADHD. First, it should be stated that the level of physical activity in the children in this research was very low. These results are consistent with the results of previous studies regarding the participation of children with ADHD (Farhangnia et al., 2020; Goulardins et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021; Mastoras et al., 2018; Sabzi et al., 2021) and indicate that these children have low health-oriented physical activity. Therefore, considering the positive effects and consequences of participation in physical activity on the physical and mental health of children, the need for interventions and strategies to increase the level of physical activity of these children is felt. Therefore, it is essential that child sports professionals take the necessary measures to improve the level of physical activity of children with ADHD.

In addition, the results of the present research showed that the level of

implementation of gross and fine motor skills in preschool children with ADHD is in the average level. It is consistent with the results of previous studies (Gallotta et al., 2018; Hernandez & Caçola, 2015; Logan et al., 2011; Morley et al., 2015; Mukherjee et al., 2017; Venetsanou & Kambas, 2016, 2017; Wrotniak et al., 2016) and indicates that these children have a low level of fine and gross motor skills. Therefore, considering the important effects of motor skills implementation on children's daily and social activities, the need for interventions and strategies to increase the level of motor skills implementation in these children is felt. Therefore, it is necessary that child sports specialists take the necessary measures to improve the level of execution of movement skills of children with ADHD.

In particular, gender differences, the results of the present research showed that girls have a lower level of physical activity than boys. Also, girls have a lower level of fine and gross motor skills than boys. These results show that regarding children with ADHD, special attention should be paid to

girls because their motor skills are lower than boys. Therefore, interventions and strategies to improve physical activity and movement skills in children with ADHD should focus and pay special attention to girls.

Regarding the effect of physical activity on the implementation of fine and gross motor skills in children with ADHD, the results of the present study showed that the greater the participation of children in physical activity, the higher their ability to perform fine and gross motor skills. These results are consistent with the results of previous research on the effect of physical activity and sports on the performance of motor skills in children (Dishman et al., 2009; Gallego-Méndez et al., 2020; Ghorbani et al., 2020; Haidar et al., 2019; Lahart et al., 2019; Schwartz et al., 2019; Sheikh et al., 2021, 2022; Wafa et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2021) and indicate the positive effect of regular participation in physical and sports activities on the performance of motor skills in children, including children with ADHD.

In general, teachers and physical education planners need to understand and recognize patterns and health factors affecting physical activity (such as motor competence, perceived competence and physical fitness related to health), because it affects the levels of physical activity and motor performance of children. Educational leaders should provide environments in which the effects of motor skills (especially gross skills) on children's physical activity are considered, and physical education teachers should implement these programs according to the age of children. Schools should have valid and relevant tools for

measuring children's motor skills. provide teachers with tools to measure progress in children's movement skills. Considering the role of perceived competence in children's tendency to physical activity, teachers should provide environments and provide suitable movement tasks, and encourage and give positive feedback from experiences (above) increasing the perceived competence of children. In the end, it should be said that it is necessary to pay more attention to these factors in physical education programs and exercises in order to improve the physical activity of male children.

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to investigate the effect of physical activity on the implementation of fine and gross motor skills in preschool children with ADHD. In summary, the results of the present research showed that preschool children with ADHD have low physical activity and moderate motor ability. Also, girls have a lower level of physical activity and motor ability than boys. These results show that the need for interventions to increase the level of physical activity and motor ability in preschool children with ADHD should be specially focused on girls. Finally, the results of this research showed that physical activity can positively affect the performance of fine and gross motor skills in preschool children with ADHD. Therefore, child professionals can use physical activity as one of the ways to improve the motor ability level of preschool children with ADHD.

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Conflict of interests

The Author declares that there is no conflict of interest with any organization. Also, this research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

- Abdi, K., Hosseini, F. B., Chaharbaghi, Z., & Ghorbani, S. (2022). Impact of Social Support on Wellbeing and Health-Related Quality of Life among Elderly Women: Mediating Role of Physical Activity. *Women's Health Bulletin*, 9(2), 104-109. <https://doi.org/10.30476/whb.2022.94981.1174>
- Baniasadi, T., Ranjbari, S., Abedini, A., Dana, A., & Ghorbani, S. (2022a). Investigation the Association of Internet Addiction with Mental Health and Physical Activity in Teenage Girls: The Mediating Role of Parental Attitude. *Women's Health Bulletin*, 9(4), 243-250. <https://doi.org/10.30476/whb.2022.96915.1197>
- Baniasadi, T., Ranjbari, S., Khajehafaton Mofrad, S., Dana, A. (2022b). Associations between device-measured physical activity and balance performance in children: Mediating role of motor self-efficacy. *Biomedical Human Kinetics*, 14(1), 252-258. <https://doi.org/10.2478/bhk-2022-0031>
- Baniasadi, T., Ranjbari, S., Khajehafaton, S., Neshati, A., & Dana, A. (2022c). Effects of Physical Activity on Adiposity in Children: Mediating Role of Self-Esteem and Body-Image. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 10(12), 17172-17181. <https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2022.67562.5043>
- Basterfield, L., Burn, N. L., Galna, B., Karoblyte, G., & Weston, K. L. (2021). The association between physical fitness, sports club participation and body mass index on health-related quality of life in primary school children from a socioeconomically deprived area of England. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 24, 101557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2021.101557>
- Birchwood, J., & Daley, D. (2012). Brief report: The impact of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) symptoms on academic performance in an adolescent community sample. *Journal of Adolescence*, 35(1), 225-231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.011>
- Brian, A., Getchell, N., True, L., De Meester, A., Stodden, D. F. (2020). Reconceptualizing and Operationalizing Seefeldt's Proficiency Barrier: Applications and Future Directions. *Sports Medicine*, 50(11), 1889-1900. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-020-01332-6>
- Bruininks, R. H., & Bruininks, B. D. (2005). *Bruininks-Oseretsky Test of Motor Proficiency, Second Edition (BOT-2)* [Database record]. APA PsycTests. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/t14991-000>
- Chaharbaghi, Z., Baniasadi, T., & Ghorbani, S. (2022). Effects of Teacher's Teaching Style in Physical Education on Moderate-to-Vigorous Physical Activity of High-School Students: an Accelerometer-based Study. *International Journal of School Health*, 9(3), 143-150.

- <https://doi.org/10.30476/intjsh.2022.95204.1224>
- Chaharbaghi, Z., Hosseini, F. B., BaniAsadi, T., Moradi, L., & Dana, A. (2022). Impact of Physical Activity on Resilience among Teenage Girls during the COVID-19 Pandemic: a Mediation by Self-Esteem. *Women's Health Bulletin*, 9(2), 80-85.
<https://doi.org/10.30476/whb.2022.94451.1166>
- De Meester, A., Stodden, D., Goodway, J., True, L., Brian, A., Ferkel, R., Haerens, L. (2018). Identifying a motor proficiency barrier for meeting physical activity guidelines in children. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*; 21(1), 58-62.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2017.05.007>
- Dishman, R. K., Saunders, R. P., Motl, R. W., Dowda, M., & Pate, R. R. (2009). Self-efficacy moderates the relation between declines in physical activity and perceived social support in high school girls. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 34(4), 441-451.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsn100>
- Farhangnia, S., Hassanzadeh, R., & Ghorbani, S. (2020). Handwriting Performance of Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: The Role of Visual-Motor Integration. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 8(11), 12317-326.
<https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2020.47633.3857>
- Gallego-Méndez, J., et al. (2020). Relationship between health-related quality of life and physical activity in children with hyperactivity. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(8)8, 2804.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/2Fijerph17082804>
- Gallotta, M. C., Baldari, C., Guidetti, L. (2018). Motor proficiency and physical activity in preschool girls: A preliminary study. *Early Child Dev Care*, 188, 1381-1391.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2016.1261337>
- Ghorbani, S., Rezaeeshirazi, R., Shakki, M., Noohpisheh, S., Farzanegi, P. (2020). The role of BMI, physical activity and the use of electronic device in the status of trunk abnormalities in male adolescents. *Journal Gorgan University of Medical Sciences*, 22(3), 129-136.
<http://goums.ac.ir/journal/article-1-3676-en.html>
- Goulardins, J. B., Marques, J. C., & De Oliveira, J. A. (2017). Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and motor impairment: A critical review. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 124(2), 425-440.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0031512517690607>
- Guadagnoli, M., Holcomb, W., & Davis, M. (2002). The efficacy of video feedback for learning the golf swing. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 20(8), 615-622.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/026404102320183176>
- Haidar, A., Ranjit, N., Archer, N., & Hoelscher, D. M. (2019). Parental and peer social support is associated with healthier physical activity behaviors in adolescents: A cross-sectional analysis of Texas School Physical Activity and Nutrition (TX SPAN) data. *BMC public health*, 19(1), 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7001-0>
- Hashemi Motlagh, S., BaniAsadi, T., Chaharbaghi, Z., & Moradi, L. (2022). The Effects of Parental Socioeconomic Status on Children' Physical Activity: Mediating Role of Motivation. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 10(8), 16538-16544.
<https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2022.63421.4834>
- Hazrati, Z., Ranjbari, S., BaniAsadi, T., & Khajehaflatan, S. (2022). Effects of Social Support on Participation of Children with ADHD in Physical Activity: Mediating Role

- of Emotional Wellbeing. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 10(10), 16880-16886. <https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2022.64698.4899>
- Hernandez, A. M., Caçola, P. (2015). Motor proficiency predicts cognitive ability in four-year-olds. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 23(4), 573–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2014.991094>
- Gritten Campos, J., Araújo Bacil, E. D., Silva Piola, T., Pereira da Silva, M., Pacífico, A. B., & de Campos, W. (2019). Social support, self-efficacy and level of physical activity of students aged 13-15 years. *Brazilian Journal of Kineanthropometry & Human Performance*, 21, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-0037.2019v21e58684>
- Khosravi, M., Seyedi Asl, S. T., Nazari Anamag, A., SabzehAra Langaroudi, M., Moharami, J., Ahmadi, S., Ganjali, A., Ghiasi, Z., Nafeli, M., Kasaeiyan, R. (2023). Parenting styles, maladaptive coping styles, and disturbed eating attitudes and behaviors: a multiple mediation analysis in patients with feeding and eating disorders. *PeerJ*, 11, e14880 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14880>
- Kowalski, K. C., Crocker, P. R., & Faulkner, R. A. (1997). Validation of the physical activity questionnaire for older children. *Pediatric Exercise Science*, 9(2), 174-186. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.9.2.174>
- Lahart, I., Darcy, P., Gidlow, C., & Calogiuri, G. (2019). The effects of green exercise on physical and mental wellbeing: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(8), 1352. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16081352>
- Li, R., Liang, X., Liu, F., Zhou, Z., Zhang, Z., Lu, Y., ... & Yang, B. (2021). Mediating effect of motor competence on the relationship between physical activity and quality of life in children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. *BioMed Research International*, 2021, 4814250. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4814250>
- Logan, S. W., Scrabis-Fletcher, K., Modlesky, C., Getchell, N. (2011). The relationship between motor skill proficiency and body mass index in preschool children. *Research Quarterly for Exercise Sport*, 82(3), 442-448. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2011.10599776>
- Mastoras, S. M., Saklofske, D. H., Schwean, V. L., & Climie, E. A. (2018). Social support in children with ADHD: An exploration of resilience. *Journal of attention disorders*, 22(8), 712-723. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1087054715611491>
- Mohammadi Orangi, B., Bahram, A., & Yaali, R. (2018). The comparison effect of BMI and age on motor proficiency in children, adolescents, and adults. *Razi Journal of Medical Sciences*, 25(9), 74-83. <http://dorl.net/dor/20.1001.1.22287043.1397.25.9.7.6>
- Mohammadi, H., Nafei, H., Baniasadi, T., & Chaharbaghi, Z. (2022). Accelerometer-Based Physical Activity and Health-Related Quality of Life in Children with ADHD. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 10(7), 16362-16369. <https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2022.63699.4847>
- Morley, D., Till, K., Ogilvie, P., Turner, G. (2015). Influences of gender and socioeconomic status on the motor proficiency of children in the UK. *Human Movement Science*, 44, 150-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2015.08.022>
- Mukherjee, S., Ting Jamie, L. C., Fong, L. H. (2017). Fundamental Motor Skill Proficiency of 6- to 9-Year-Old Singaporean Children. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 124(3), 584-600. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0031512517703005>
- Sabzi, A., Dana, A., Salehian, M., Shaygan Yekta, H. (2021). The Effect of Water

- Treadmill Exercise on Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 9(6), 13671-13681. <https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2021.57015.4466>
- Saeedpour-Parizi, M. R., Hassan, S. E., Azad, A. et al. (2021). Target position and avoidance margin effects on path planning in obstacle avoidance. *Scientific Reports*, 11, 15285. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-94638-y>
- Saeedpour-Parizi, M. R., Hassan, S.E., Baniasadi, T. et al. (2020). Hierarchical goal effects on center of mass velocity and eye fixations during gait. *Experimental Brain Research*, 238, 2433–2443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-020-05900-0>
- Schwartz, J., Rhodes, R., Bredin, S. S., Oh, P., & Warburton, D. E. (2019). Effectiveness of approaches to increase physical activity behavior to prevent chronic disease in adults: a brief commentary. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 8(3), 295. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8030295>
- Seyedi Asl, S. T., Rahnejat, A. M., Elikae, M. M., Khademi, M., Shahed-HaghGhadam, H., Taghva, A. (2021). The role of resilience, positive/negative emotions, and character strengths in predicting burnout of military personnel. *EBNESINA*; 22 (4), 4-13. https://ebnesina.ajaums.ac.ir/browse.php?a_code=A-10-689-1&sid=1&slc_lang=en
- Seyedi Asl, S. T., Sadeghi, K., Bakhtiari, M., Ahmadi, S. M., Nazari Anamagh, A., Khayatan, T. (2016). Effect of Group Positive Psychotherapy on Improvement of Life Satisfaction and The Quality of Life in Infertile Woman. *International Journal of Fertility and Sterility*, 10(1), 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.22074%2Fijfs.2016.4775>
- Sheikh, M., Bay, N., Ghorbani, S., & Esfahani nia, A. (2022). Effects of Social Support and Physical Self-efficacy on Physical Activity of Adolescents. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 10(4), 15823-15834. <https://doi.org/10.22038/ijp.2022.62762.4793>
- Sheikh, M., Bay, N., Ghorbani, S., Esfahaninia, A. (2021). Effects of Peers on Motivation and Physical Activity Behavior of Adolescent Students: An Investigation of Trans-Contextual Model. *International Journal of School Health*, 8(1), 47-54. <https://doi.org/10.30476/intjsh.2021.90210.1129>
- Slotte, S., Sääkslahti, A., Metsämuuronen, J., Rintala, P. (2015). Fundamental movement skill proficiency and body composition measured by dual energy X-ray absorptiometry in eight-year-old children. *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(3), 475-485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2014.936428>
- Taghva, A., Seyedi Asl, S. T., Rahnejat, A. M., Elikae, M. M. (2020). Resilience, Emotions, and Character Strengths as Predictors of Job Stress in Military Personnel. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences*, 14(2), e86477. <https://doi.org/10.5812/ijpbs.86477>
- Venetsanou, F., & Kambas, A. (2016). Motor proficiency in young children: A closer look at potential gender differences. *Sage Open*, 6(1), 2158244015626226. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244015626226>
- Venetsanou, F., & Kambas, A. (2017). Can motor proficiency in preschool age affect physical activity in adolescence?. *Pediatric Exercise Science*, 29(2), 254-259. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2016-0119>
- Wafa, S. W. W.b. S. S. T., Shahril, M. R. b., Ahmad, A. b. et al. (2016). Association between physical activity and health-related quality of life in children: a cross-sectional study. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 14(71), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-016-0474-y>

- Wrotniak, B. H., Epstein, L. H., Dorn, J. M., Jones, K. E., & Kondilis, V. A. (2006). The relationship between motor proficiency and physical activity in children. *Pediatrics*, *118*(6), e1758-e1765. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2006-0742>
- Zhang, X., Tan, S. S., Franse, C. B., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Verma, A., Williams, G., ... & Raat, H. (2021). Longitudinal association between physical activity and health-related quality of life among community-dwelling older adults: a longitudinal study of Urban Health Centres Europe (UHCE). *BMC Geriatrics*, *21*(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-021-02452-y>